

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF TRENDS IN EMERGING RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT

Volume 2; Issue 1; 2024; Page No. 140-146

Received: 15-12-2023

Accepted: 27-02-2024

An ecological concern & imperialism in Arundhati Roy's selected works

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12794755>

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Abstract

The kinship between nature and literature is age-old. Almost every literary genre such as poetry, drama, fiction and non-fiction has been dealing with themes about nature or environment. However, the twentieth century has witnessed a great number of incidents of degradation of natural environment in the wake of industrial and technological development all around the world. Literature has constantly been recording the ecological disasters caused by human beings. Various fictional and nonfictional writings have criticized human activities responsible for the destruction of nature and supporting ecosystems. Many contemporary writers have written dedicatedly about emerging ecological concerns in their works. Among them, Arundhati Roy is completely devoted to throw light on various ecological issues through her essays. In the history of Indian English Prose tradition, she has achieved an enviable position as an essayist with her political and environment works. In view of this, the present research paper aims to trace the ecological imperialism in Arundhati Roy's works. This research paper mainly focuses on the destructive aftermaths of numerous development projects on environment as well as on those who live in close association with the environment such as tribal communities. It offers a trenchant critique of imperial forces of neocolonialism which subjugate country's natural resources; depletion of environment caused by various dam and mining and ostracism of a large number of indigenous people from the places of their natural habitat.

Keywords: Arundhati Roy, ecological, imperialism, environment

Introduction

The Oxford English dictionary defines colonialism as "an alleged policy of exploitation of backward or weak people by a large power." It has a very negative connotation in postcolonial studies, where it is used interchangeably with racism, oppression, injustice, and exploitation. In the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries, colonialism refers to the violent seizure and exploitation of indigenous peoples and territories by European powers. It is a potent form of exploitation founded on differences in political systems, technological advancements, cultural forms of knowledge, and racial differences.

Imperialism is a phrase that is frequently used to refer to colonialism, more or less properly. Another example of imperialism is when a European nation rules over a non-European one. Nonetheless, imperialism frequently alludes to the process of governing by remote control, frequently without real colonization of non-European territories. It denotes that a major European or American force dominates

the political, economic, military, and cultural spheres of influence in countries in Asia, Africa, or South America. Only in the latter half of the 1800s did the term imperialism gain widespread use. These days, it primarily refers to an economic dominance and exploitation system, though political and military dominance may coexist with the economic one. The economic demands of the European nation are the driving force behind imperialism. Imperialism was motivated by the desire to amass more riches, whereas colonialism was driven by the necessity to establish a new living area. The purposeful mercenary spread of European power into non-European lands was known as imperialism. We have obtained political independence, or the transfer of power from Europeans to Native Americans, as a result of the freedom struggle.

Nonetheless, the European power continues to exert economic dominance over the indigenous population. In other words, despite their formal freedom, 'free' nation states nonetheless face economic exploitation at the hands of

'imperial' European countries. For this reason, the phrase "post-imperial" is never used. The term "neo-colonialism" has been used to characterize this type of control, specifically in reference to American dominance over the rest of the world. The ongoing economic exploitation of nation-states in Asia and Africa by European and American powers is known as neo-colonialism. The "colonies" are actually not colonies; rather, they are still dependent on and exploited by their former overlords. Neo-colonialism is typically accomplished via a connection between the chief executive officer, the banker, the politician, and the general in addition to governmental control.

Edward Said distinguishes between colonialism and imperialism in Culture and Imperialism.

Imperialism means the practice, the theory, and the attitudes of a dominating metropolitan center ruling a distant territory; colonialism, which is almost always a consequence of imperialism, is the implanting of settlements on distant territory (9).

Tradesmen have long benefited from the abundance of commodities found on the Indian subcontinent. These traders came from all over the world, with many Europeans being among them. The Mughal Empire lost some of its authority in the fifteenth and eighteenth centuries. Particularly among the Muslims and Hindus, there was discontent among the subjects. The internal discontent among the populace was observed by the European traders. They capitalized on the discontent among the populace. The British had not the slightest interest in controlling India; they had come for business. In order to facilitate the transportation of commodities by sea to their home country, colonies were built along our nation's shore. The British were astute and competent artisans. Relationships with the aboriginal population were forged via commerce and involvement in various regional religious and cultural events. They won over the hearts of the locals with this tactic. The Indians' internal strife and conflicts were noted by the British. These astute individuals used this circumstance. "Divide and rule" was the enacted policy. This policy performed like magic. They founded the East India Company with Robert Clive as its leader as a result of the policy's success. The business gradually expanded its reach across the nation. By building an army, the corporation forced the French to retreat from India. The business set up government around the nation by utilizing the Mughal Empire. The Indians were enlisted into their army as sepoys, or soldiers.

The British had been to India for commerce, as was previously mentioned. During that time, Europe saw the Industrial Revolution. The industrial revolution raised Britain's need for raw materials. There was now a market for the made goods. The ideal place to meet their needs was India. The Mughal Empire began to crumble in the eighteenth century. As a result, the British were able to consolidate their control over the Indian Territory. The British used various land revenue practices on the farmers, making the impoverished farmers increasingly poorer, in order to carry out their goal through wars, treaties, annexation, and other means. The British were paid a substantial amount. The development of cash crops and raw

materials for British industry led to the commercialization of agriculture. With their tremendous political clout, the British were able to dominate trade with India. They eliminated competition by trading victories over their foreign competitors. They purchased raw materials at discounted prices and assumed control over the selling of all varieties. Conversely, the Indian weavers were compelled to pay exorbitant amounts for the identical raw material. By imposing high tariffs on Indian goods entering the country, Britain was able to safeguard its domestic industry. To make it easier to move manufactured goods from the ports to the market and raw materials from fields to the ports, the nation's transportation and communication infrastructure was upgraded. In order to manage their growing business, the British required more personnel. For it, persons with education were required. The study of English language was essential for this. To do this, instruction in English was introduced. The plan was to produce a class of well-educated, English-speaking individuals who would help them maintain political control over India and help rule the nation. This aided the British in establishing, preserving, and expanding their dominance over India. Because British commodities entered the Indian market duty-free whereas Indian items-especially handicrafts-were substantially taxed upon export, the British were able to sell their goods at lower prices. Additionally, in response to demand from British manufacturers, the British put a protective tariff on Indian textiles. As a result of these regulations, India quickly transitioned from being a clothing exporter to an importer of British clothing and an exporter of raw cotton. The Indian handloom and textile industries suffered greatly as a result. Many laborers and weavers associated with this enterprise lost their jobs. These talented artisans who were out of job were compelled to relocate to the countryside in order to labor on farms. The British desired for India to be a buyer of their products. As a result, jobs in the paper, metal, and textile industries quickly disappeared. The international market for Indian handicrafts was lost. Indian products were unable to compete with British factory-made ones.

Agriculture was India's primary source of income and subsistence for generations. All the rulers of the world had relied mostly on land revenue for their income. The British continued to periodically raise land revenue in India. The farmers' lives had descended into misery. Farmers were required to divide their produce with landowners and collectors. In such cases, the local government was powerless to provide the impoverished in rural areas with justice. A significant economic consequence of British strategy was the introduction of numerous cash crops, including oil-seed, tea, coffee, indigo, opium, jute, and sugarcane. Several goals were behind the introduction of cash crops. Chinese tea was traded for Indian opium. The British businessmen had tight control over the opium market. The earnings from opium cultivation were not available to Indian farmers. In addition, the farmers were made to grow indigo and urged to sell it under their own terms. Britain received the shipment of indigo for use in dyeing. The British instituted a system for growing indigo, requiring farmers to plant it on three-fifteenths of their land. For a while, the ground was become unproductive due to indigo cultivation. Tea was another lucrative crop. The tea plantation's ownership changed frequently. The laborers

endured great hardships while working on these plantations. The commercialization of agriculture has improved land ownership transfers. The farmers became landless laborers as a result. Many dealers, middlemen, and merchants took advantage of the opportunity. Food grain output decreased as a result of the production of cash crops. From our land, precious wealth was carried to Britain. In order to cover the costs of salaries, pensions, military and civilian staff training, and other expenses related to their control over India, the British placed additional financial strain on the Indian people. Their collection was substantial enough to alter our nation's economic situation.

In order for the Indians to purchase items made in their nation, the British desired for them to be modern and educated. The Indian concepts were considered antiquated and inferior by the British, who thought that western ideas and culture were contemporary and superior. Indians actually have a wealth of traditional knowledge that endures to this day. Indian culture was and still is unparalleled. The English perceived the Indians as uncivilized and primitive. However, some English people's attitude toward the Indians was humanistic. The Radicals wanted the Indians to be a part of the contemporary, forward-thinking scientific community and to be integrated into the global mainstream. The Indians were very carefully brought towards modernity by the British. They were afraid that excessive meddling with their culture and religious values might escalate into violence. They were really interested in bringing English to India. One element of their plan was to teach the Indians English. They were aware that Indians with limited English proficiency would labor for them as clerks and assistants for pitiful pay. Additionally, it was anticipated to produce a class of Indians who would support the British. The Indians in this class would learn to respect British culture and viewpoints. Additionally, the intention was for this class to contribute to the growth of the British products market. Their goal was for education to fortify India's political foundations. The British believed that by educating the English-speaking Indians, they would be able to establish British culture among the masses and use this educated class as a means of governing India. The English who knew Indians were given jobs by the British. In order to obtain employment, many Indians turned to English schooling. English education eventually turned into a monopoly of the wealthy living in big cities and a status symbol.

The British psyche is revealed in the following speech made by Macaulay to the British parliament of the time

I have travelled across the length and breadth of India and I have not seen one person who is a beggar, who is a thief, such wealth I have seen in this country, such high moral values, people of such caliber, that I do not think we would ever conquer this country, unless we break the very backbone of this nation, which is her spiritual and cultural heritage, and, therefore, I propose that we replace her old and ancient education system, her culture, for if the Indians think that all that is foreign and English is good and greater than their own, they will lose their self-esteem, their native culture and they will become what we want them, a truly dominated nation (Lindsay, n.p.).

Neo-colonialism, as it exists today, is imperialism at its riskiest. In Toto, traditional colonialism is still in place.

Neo-colonialism has replaced colonialism as the primary tool of imperialism in modern times. The fundamental characteristic of neo-colonialism is the autonomous state that possesses all the external attributes of international sovereignty. Actually, outside forces control its political system and thus its economy. The manufactured goods of the imperialist power must be adopted by the neo-colonialist states at the expense of rival goods from other sources. Neo-colonialism has the effect of utilizing foreign capital not for the development of the world's developing or less developed nations, but rather for their exploitation. Neo-colonialism's investment policies widen the divide between the world's rich and impoverished nations. Using high rates of interest is another neo-colonialist tactic. According to World Bank statistics from 1962, 71 nations in Asia, Africa, and Latin America owed around \$27,000 million in foreign debt, of which \$5,000 million was paid in interest and service costs. These foreign debts have since been valued in these regions at about £30,000 million. Nearly three-quarters of the loans made by the major imperialist powers had interest rates of more above five percent in 1961; in some cases, these rates reached seven or eight percent. These loans also had burdensomely short call-in periods.

Multilateral aid through international organizations has emerged as yet another neo-colonialist economic trap. Examples of these organizations include the International Development Association, the International Monetary Fund, the International Finance Corporation, and the World Bank, which are primarily financed by U.S. capital. These agencies routinely compel prospective borrowers to comply with a litany of obnoxious requirements, including providing economic data, submitting company plans and policies for World Bank approval, and agreeing to agency oversight of their loan utilization. Regarding the purported development, applicants were promised a total of \$500 million by the International Development Association between 1960 and mid-1963; of this amount, only \$70 million was really received.

As was already mentioned, colonial control severely impoverished the Indian populace and wrecked the country's economy. When Western colonization began, India was an affluent country. The following description of Indian life can be found in the 17th-century French traveler Tavernier's *Travels in India*:

Even in the smallest villages, rice, flour, butter, milk, beans and other vegetables, sugar and sweetmeats can be procured in abundance (qtd. in Faleiro).

In such cases, what should the developing nations do? Ecological imperialism in the developed and developing countries of Asia and Africa stems from the issues previously highlighted. Another significant victim of ecological imperialism is India. Very few Indian authors have addressed this topic in their works. India has been significantly impacted by the ecological imperialism issue.

In her writings, Arulndhati Roy has addressed themes that the public finds troubling. She is one of the most vocal and well-known opponents of globalization in existence today. Globalization gives rise to ecological imperialism. She mounts a polemical research and writing campaign to highlight the hidden costs and negative effects of global capitalism, counting its catastrophic toll on India's rural poor and the environment. Her varied pieces reflect her concerns

on a range of issues, including terrorism, globalization, nuclear disarmament, global capitalism, the false promises of large dams, the drawbacks of corporate globalization, and the US government's fight against terrorism.

In her essay "The End of Imagination," Roy discusses her serious worries regarding nuclear testing in India. This essay is a reasoned, yet emotionally charged, plea for everyone to take a closer look at what has been going on. The use of nuclear weapons will eliminate both adversaries and assailants. The land in India will be destroyed if these weapons are employed against Pakistan or other neighboring states because of their physical proximity and river connections. The sky, air, earth, wind, and water-the fundamental elements-will all turn against each other. These elements will have dreadful fury. For days, the farms, villages, forests, and towns will all burn. Rivers will become toxic. Fire will rise from the air. The flames will spread due to the wind. Smoke will ascend and block the sun once all that can burn has burned out and the fires have put out. Roy (2001(a):5-6). The Indian government is the sole fresh development on the old horizon. The Indian Prime Minister claims that a "deteriorating security environment" was the reason behind India's decision to proceed with nuclear tests in an egregiously smug letter to the President of the United States. The Prime Minister continues by bringing up the 1962 conflict with China as well as the "three aggressions that have been suffered in the last fifty years (from Pakistan)." And over the past ten years, particularly in Jammu and Kashmir, we have been the victims of ceaseless acts of terrorism and militancy funded by it." Ibid., 22-23. The United States of America exercises its veto authority over all other nations. These are the individuals whose pasts are stained with other people's blood. They essentially invented everything, including colonialism, apartheid, slavery, ethnic cleansing, germ warfare, and chemical weapons. They have destroyed entire people, destroyed civilizations, and pillaged entire continents. They know they have more money, food, and bigger bombs than anybody else, so they stand on the global stage completely nude but with no shame. They are aware that they have all it takes to destroy us throughout a typical workday. In my opinion, it is more conceit than hypocrisy (Ibid: 24-25).

The issue's many facets-rehabilitation, hydrology, drainage, water-logging, catchment area treatment, passion, and politics-have been appropriated by experts and consultants, who then take them to their hideouts to defend them ferociously from the uninvited curiosity of interested laypeople (Ibid:51). Consider the paradox: despite spending billions of rupees building dams, the situation remains unchanged.

...forty percent of all the Big Dams being built in the world are being built in India. Yet one-fifth of our population does not have safe drinking water and two-thirds lack basic sanitation (Ibid: 56-57).

The Ministers and their close associates now own the enormous forests and numerous other priceless resources. It doesn't appear that we are aware that the resources we are consuming are limited and running out quickly. Ibid., p. 70. India's cities are home to her people. India's villages exist solely to support her urban centers. Her peasants must be

kept under control and preserved, but only justly, as they are the vassals of her residents (Ibid: 71).

Regardless one perspective, the Narmada Valley Development Project is a large undertaking. It will change the ecosystem of one of the largest rivers in India throughout its whole basin. It will have an impact on the lives of 25 million valley residents, for better or ill. Ibid., p. 75 The Government of India and landless laborers are essentially the same in that the former uses the money to exist, while the latter simply directs it into the personal bank accounts of its officials and agents, locking the nation into an economic shackle from which it may never free itself (Ibid:77). China is currently their most favored customer. The great irony of our times is that while Americans condemn the tragedy in Tiananmen Square, the Bank will utilize their funds to finance the construction of China's Three Gorges Dam, which will force 1.3 million people to relocate. (Source: 78) In 1993, the Pergau Dam in Malaysia was funded by a discounted loan of 234 million pounds from Britain, even though a report by the Overseas Development Administration stated that the dam would be a "bad buy" for Malaysia. Subsequently, it was revealed that the loan was provided in an attempt to 'convince' Malaysia to sign a 1.3-billion-pound deal to purchase British arms. (Source: 79) This is an example of Roy's in-depth research on the plight of the impoverished. They age and become sick. even the early age of premature death. The ragged army in the valley has been living in constant fear of being evicted for the past twenty years, ever since the Tribunal's award. Most places have shown no signs of "development" for the past 20 years: no roads, no schools, no wells, and no access to healthcare. It has been separated from the rest of society for twenty years due to the stigma of being "slated for submergence" (no marriage proposals, no land transactions). When the 'fruits of modern development' did arrive, they brought nothing but dread (Ibid: 91). People who relied on the forests for their livelihood were forced to leave as they continued to be cut down and hauled away on trucks, with the forests set to submerge. The dam's effects on the environment and the people who live along the river are already severe, despite the fact that it is nowhere near its final, intended height (Ibid: 100).

Historically, rice, fruit, and vegetables have been grown by landless people (mostly tribal people and Dalits) on the fertile, shallow silt banks that the river leaves behind when it recedes during the dry months. The engineers in charge of the Bargi Dam, which is located far upstream and close to Jabalpur, periodically unexpectedly release water from the reservoir. The river's water level abruptly rises downstream. Numerous crops have been washed away, leaving hundreds of individuals without a means of subsistence (Ibid: 101). Their daily income is between ten and twenty rupees, which they use to support and feed their families, as opposed to a forest where they could gather everything they needed, including food, fuel, fodder, rope, gum, tobacco, tooth powder, medicinal herbs, and building materials. There's a hand pump there instead of a river. They were covered even though they had no money in their home villages. They had the forests and the river to fish in if the rains did not come. Their fixed deposit was their livestock. They would be in financial ruin in a heartbeat without all of this (Ibid: 105-106). He was listing the fruits he used to collect in the forest

for me to see. He made a total of 48 types. He told me he didn't think he would ever be able to afford to eat fruit again, nor his children. Unless he took it, no. What was wrong with his baby, I questioned him? He stated that having the infant live this way would be preferable to its dying. I wanted to know what the mother of the infant thought about that. She did not respond. She did nothing but look. (Source: 106) The lack of research into the downstream environment, including the riverine ecosystem, its seasonal variations, biological species, and the patterns of resource usage, horrified the Morse Committee. The project's builders had no clue how the dam would affect the environment and people downstream, much less what measures to take to lessen such effects (Ibid: 118–119).

Hilsa's upbringing depends on obtaining spawn from wild adults, which the dam will most likely eradicate. One-fifth of freshwater fish worldwide have been wiped out or put in risk due to dams (Ibid: 119). Instead of cultivating food they can afford to eat, people are starting to plant only food they can sell. They forfeit control over their life when they identify with the "market" (Ibid: 121). Regretfully, this is a poisonous payoff in terms of ecology. The earth gives out, even if the markets do. It eventually gets too impoverished to withstand the increased demands placed upon it. The soil gradually loses nutrients and quality, the athlete who uses steroids becomes disabled, and agricultural yields start to fall (Ibid: 121). Estimates for India range from 6 to 10 million hectares. Over 52% of the Sardar Sarovar command area is vulnerable to salinization and water-logging, according to "secret" government studies (Ibid: 122). Seventeen of the nineteen acres that Bhaiji Bhai, a farmer in the Kevadiya community near the Sardar Sarovar dam, had were taken by the Wonder Canal. Bhaiji Bhai and his community, made to grin for pictures that appear on official calendars. The grace of fury was denied to Bhaiji Bhai and his people. Smashed like bugs by this nation they are meant to call their own, Bhaiji Bhai and his people (Ibid: 133). You can grasp the price being paid for things in the fitness of things, regardless of how much you love or loathe the dam or whether you want it or not. If you possess the bravery to observe as the books are squared and the debts are paid (Ibid: 137). Roy makes valid, worthwhile, and universal points.

Another insightful essay by Roy discusses the place of writers in society and is titled "The Ladies have feelings so.. Shall we leave it to the Experts." The essay discusses globalization and exposes its flaws in the governance structure by critiquing it in detail. The nation's governing structure is in charge of overseeing globalization within its borders. Roy takes a firm stance against the globalization phenomena that is being applied everywhere. According to her, resistance is the only thing standing between the extremely exploitative processes taking place under the guise of globalization and a check. She adopts a strong pro-people position and uses striking images to persuade the reader.

Large companies controlled by powerful businessmen have devastated thousands of people's livelihoods that depend on these resources for a living by poisoning and depleting groundwater, deforested woods, and polluted waterways. The Orient Paper Mill in Madhya Pradesh, the Grasim mill in Kerala, and the toxic industries found in Gujarat's

"sunrise belt" the hundreds of other uranium mines in Jaduguda, the aluminum plants in Orissa, etc. (Ibid: 208). Even though pollution has made life harder for innocent bystanders, there is no severe legislation that can prohibit pollution. Different pollution boards serve no purpose.

Roy's essay "Power Politics: The Reincarnation of Rumpelstiltskin" is another captivating piece. She conjures up the idea of a power-hungry demon by drawing inspiration from the legend of Rumpelstiltskin from Europe. In the tale of Rumpelstiltskin, a young lady is tasked with the impossibility of turning straw into gold and is warned that failure to do so will result in her death. Three times she is helped by an odd little man who demands the first child she has in return for his assistance. She agrees since there isn't anything else she can do to save her life, but she doesn't recall her promise to the gnome until after the baby is delivered. He informs her that she can keep the child if she can do one thing: guess his name, as she begs him. Rumpelstiltskin is a concept, a fragment of aberrant, sneaky, Caucasian reasoning that will ultimately destroy itself. But for the time being, he's fine. His domain is unprocessed wealth, his captures new markets, his beseeches revenues, his frontiers are unbounded, and his armaments are nuclear (Ibid: 145–146). In March 2000, the US President paid a visit to India. The Indian government removed import restrictions on 1,400 goods, including milk, grain, sugar, and cotton, just before the visit-despite the fact that there was an abundance of sugar and cotton this year and that 42.5 million tons of grain were rotting in government storage facilities. Around US \$3 billion worth of transactions were signed during The Visit (Ibid: 147–148). The World Water Forum was held in Holland to address a range of water-related issues. A noble discussion had place over the inclusion of drinking water as a Basic Human Right. Our nation is in a different circumstance. The lines that follow highlight the significance and necessity of water.

...there is a difference between valuing water and putting a market value on water. No one values water more than a village woman who has to walk miles to fetch it. No one values it less than urban folk who pay for it to flow endlessly at the turn of a tap (Ibid: 150-151).

In the liminal zone between what they say and what they sell, they (the First World) reproduce and thrive. They are advocating not just for the privatization of vital infrastructure and natural resources, but also for the privatization of the policy-making process itself. The goal of dam builders is to dictate public water policy. Financial organizations want to oversee government disinvestment, while power utility businesses want to create power policies (Ibid: 152). What is the true meaning of privatization? In essence, it is the State's transfer of productive public assets to private enterprises. Natural resources such as the air, water, forest, and earth are productive assets. The State maintains these resources in confidence for the people it represents. Seventy percent of people in a nation like India reside in rural areas. Which comes to 700 million people. Access to natural resources is directly related to their quality of life. Snatching things away and selling them to private firms as stock is an unprecedentedly brutal act of dispossession (Ibid: 153). The city of Cochin's

municipal water delivery system was privatized by the Bolivian government in 1999, and a 40-year lease was inked with the large US engineering company Bechtel. Tripping the cost of water was Bechtel's first action. It was just too expensive for hundreds of thousands of individuals (Ibid: 153). Banzer imposed martial law in April 2000. The demonstration went on. Bechtel eventually had to leave its offices. Presently, it is attempting to coerce the Bolivian government into paying it a \$12 million exit fee (Ibid: 154). Rumpelstiltskin has lofty ideas. He's stalking mega-games today: armaments, power plants, dams, mines, seeds (he wants to own life and the process of reproduction), biodiversity, public water supply systems, telecommunications, biodiversity, and the industrial infrastructure supporting all of this (Ibid: 154). India saw General Electric (GE) chairman John Welch on television. He urged, touchingly, "Don't do it for GE's sake, do it for yourselves." He continued by saying that the only way to connect India's one billion people to the digital network was to privatize the electricity sector. "I beg and pray to the Indian Government to improve infrastructure," he concluded. He was saying, of course, "You are a market of one billion customers. If you don't buy our equipment, we will miss the next revolution." Would someone kindly inform him that of his one billion "customers," 400 million are illiterate, 200 million lack access to safe drinking water, and you can talk about information and intellectual capital, but without the power to drive it, you will miss the next revolution? It's hardly the first thing on their minds to be brought into the "digital framework" (Ibid: 155).

India's planners take great pride in the fact that the country uses 20 times more electricity now than it did fifty years ago. It serves as a progress indicator for them. The fact that 70% of rural families still lack electricity is left out of their discussion. Over 85% of the poorest population, primarily Dalit and Adivasi households, live without power in the poorest states of Bihar, Uttar Pradesh, Orissa, and Rajasthan. What a disgraceful, startling record for the largest democracy in the world. Surveys by the government predict that 61 villages will be submerged in the Maheshwar Dam's reservoir. The remainder will lose their farmlands, while thirteen will be completely inundated. As is customary, not a single community was told about the dam or that they would soon be forced to leave. Under the pretense that a railway line was being built, the initial surveys were carried out. The villagers didn't realize this until 1997, when construction started on the dam, at which point the NBA in Maheshwar got underway. The survey is being conducted by the same agency that oversaw the surveys for the Bargi reservoir. What transpired there is known to us (Ibid: 173). The first of the 61 villages that will be submerged in the dam's reservoir is Jalud. Twelve families, the majority Dalit, with modest holdings close to the dam site had their land taken as early as 1985. When they objected, the police forcibly took over the land, crushed their standing crops, and filled their water lines with cement. These days, all 12 families are landless and dependent on wage labor. There has been no attempt by the new 'private' endeavor to assist them (Ibid: 175).

This small man is Rumpelstiltskin, and Roy has brought him back to represent global politics. Roy characterizes him as the all-powerful, unforgiving king that no one has ever seen

before—the representation of the aristocratic nation, the one who forces the victims to make unaffordable promises. The young lady represents India, a victim with remarkably limited choices. From this vantage point, Roy keeps addressing the main issues surrounding the debate over public water supplies to Third World countries, the challenge of poverty in the global economic and social system, and the ongoing global struggle for fundamental human rights. Roy expresses her opinions about the inequities and shortcomings of global politics through her audacious writing style. The "Rumpelstiltskins" want the "just reward" that the victims were forced to give but are now unable to provide. She uses the knowledge of the bizarre little gnome to demonstrate how the political powers in the world are making fun of the people they control. She contends that there is an urgent need to change the political and economic agreements between the "first" and "third" worlds.

"Mr. The essay "Chidambaram's War" shows the darker aspect of the Dandakaranya woodlands. Roy highlights a few situations that highlight the government's imperialist mindset when it comes to acting on behalf of massive multinational corporations. These territories have long been home to the impoverished indigenous people known as the Maoists.

"The single biggest internal security challenge ever faced by the country," according to Indian Prime Minister Man Mohan Singh, is these impoverished indigenous people (Roy: 2011:3). Why? Because 'if Left Wing extremism continues to flourish in important parts of our country, which have tremendous natural resources of minerals and other precious things, that will certainly affect the climate for Investment'(Ibid: 3. The state fears that if these adivasis are not removed from these forests and mountains then the minerals buried there would never come out. These mountains are being leased to mega mining companies with hidden share of the state stakeholders. The Maoists' army is made up of desperately poor people. These poor are living in conditions of chronic hunger. These people do not have access to education, health care or legal redress even after more than sixty years of independence. They are people who have been mercilessly exploited for decades, consistently cheated by small businessmen and moneylenders. The women are raped by police and forest department personnel. If the tribal have taken up arms, they have done so because a government that has given them nothing but violence and neglect, now wants to snatch away the last thing they have – their land. The tribal know that the roads built through their forests in Dantewada by the National Mineral Development Corporation are not for them or their children to walk on. These roads like the runways are for their heavily loaded trucks. The tribal believe that if they don't fight for their land, they will be annihilated. That is why they have taken up arms. They are fighting for survival. This is a fight for social justice, equality, protection, security and local development.

The tribals believe they have the right to defend their homes and their land. They believe that they deserve justice. But, in order to keep its better-off citizens absolutely safe, the government has declared war on these 'dangerous' people. There is no whisper of 'talks' or 'negotiations'. After Mumbai 26/11, the government was prepared to talk with

Pakistan. It is willing to talk to China. But when it comes to waging war against the poor, it's playing hard-ball. The Special Police is scouring the forest with a license to kill. The CRPF, BSF and the notorious Naga Battalion have already wreaked havoc and committed unconscionable atrocities in remote forest villages. It is not enough that the government supports and arms the Salwa Judum, the 'people's militia' that has killed and raped and burned its way through the forests of Dantewada, leaving 50,000 people in roadside police camps and 3,00,000 people homeless. IAF have been given the right to fire in 'Self-defense', the very right that the government denies its poorest citizens. Not much news comes out of these forests. Those who go in are being beaten and arrested. They are called Maoists. The state uses the purposeful exaggeration of the Maoists' threat to justify its militarization of the police, paramilitary, and noncombatant civilians alike. The poorest people will perish in this Rich People's War, and the resources it consumes will destroy the nation's economy. (When arms are purchased to fight tribal people, tax payer money is used, but the profits primarily go to multi-nationals. This is a transfer of wealth from the poor to the rich, all under the pretense of development. In Gujarat, in 2002, Hindu mobs led by the Bajrang Dal and VHP killed more people than the Maoists have ever before, but only Maoists are classified as terrorists because the others do not pose a threat to the state. Each year, thousands of farmers take their own lives. Instead of taking action, the Indian government and media seem more at ease with the idea that the impoverished should commit suicide out of desperation. Her writing is so fluid, her grasp of world politics so acute, and her opposition to nuclear weapons, environmental attacks, and the never-ending suffering of the impoverished so poignant, that her articles are as inspiring as they are energizing. "Not some bleeding heart fantasy but a largely unreported consequence of big business pounding the voiceless down to compost level," is how she describes globalization (Ghosh: 2009:120).

Conclusion

As we know, India is a home to millions of wildlife animals and plants. It has a rich variety of ecosystems. Moreover, many indigenous tribes have been living in peace with natural environment since ages. Both environment and adivasis supplement to the growth and well-being of one another. To sum up, the present paper mainly focuses on how a great number of ecosystems as well as tribal communities have been displaced by various development projects since Independence in India. The unsustainable growth and development leads to the ostracism of millions of poor marginalised people and leaving a number of wildlife species on the verge of extinction and elopement. The selected works present a pathetic image of ecological destruction and demolition by various dams, mining and other irrigation projects from past few decades. In her works, Roy makes the reader understand the whole political scenario which is at work behind the whole discourse of national development. She puts forward the role of numerous neo-liberal forces to create destruction on the name of development in third world countries. They have been continuously exploiting country's natural resources.

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